

“SMART CITY” PROJECTS IN THE KARABAKH REGION: A MODEL OF GREEN ENERGY AND DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The projects of the Smart City and the Smart Village introduced to the Karabakh region are one of the primary focuses of the modern urban development policy and sustainable regional planning strategy in Azerbaijan. The announcement of the region as a Green Energy Zone in 2021 has made the development of renewable energy sources a priority and the use of new energy and management systems grounded on digital technologies. Between 2021 and 2025, as part of the process of restoring and modernizing the electricity infrastructure of the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions, construction of hydropower, solar, and wind power plants have been conducted on a large scale. The present article will introduce the key renewable energy projects which were launched in the region throughout this period, the capacity they were installed at, as well as how they may be integrated into the energy system in the context of the idea of the smart city. Moreover, the degrees of solar and wind energy opportunities in the area are considered. The role of green energy and digital infrastructure in the creation of the model of the smart city in the Karabakh region and the perspectives of the future development in this direction are discussed, based on statistical data and official sources

Keywords: Karabakh, smart city, green energy zone, digital transformation, sustainable urban development.

Introduction. Urbanization has increased at a faster rate in the 21st century. The statistics provided by the United Nations reveal that over 50 percent of the global population resides in urban areas, and this number is expected to grow [4]. The urbanization of cities exacerbates the problems of increasing energy consumption, the increase of waste production, and the air and water pollution. The old models of management are no longer adequate in case of these challenges. The introduction of the digital technologies into the urban systems provides the opportunity to build sustainable and ecologically efficient urban models. In the new age, digitalization and urbanization are the major forces of development in the world. The rapid urbanization has aggravated issues of high energy use, carbon emissions, and ecological balance, and overloading of infrastructure. UN data indicates that about 75 percent of all of the energy used in the world is used by cities, and over 70 percent of all greenhouse gas emissions are produced by cities [4]. In this regard, strategic implementation of sustainable and environmentally oriented urban models has taken a strategic drive.

The reconstruction of the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan, which were not occupied, is not confined to the restoration of infrastructure but is also marked by the use of the modern and innovative model of urban development. In the declaration of the region as a Green Energy Zone in 2021, the goal is to focus on alternative sources of energy and to make the environment sustainable. The official statistics shows that the potential of the region in terms of renewable energy is estimated at over

10,000 MW, and over 17.5 billion AZN were planned to be spent on the reconstruction of the Karabakh region in 2021-2024 (more than 4 billion AZN in 2025) [3]. The investments are related to the reconstruction of infrastructure, power projects, the construction of international airports, and residential complexes in the Karabakh zone.

This thesis discusses the projects of Smart City and Smart Village applied in the Karabakh region in relation to the use of alternative energy sources, building of digital infrastructure, and the use of environmental standards and evaluates the relevance of the region as a model of sustainable urban development in accordance with the statistical indicators.

Energy Potential. Since 2020, the reconstruction and rebuilding of the energy base in the Karabakh region has turned into one of the priority spheres of strategic significance to the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Presidential Decree of May 3, 2021, made the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions a Green Energy Zone [6].

Between 2021 and 2025, priority in the Karabakh and East Zangezur regions has been given to the construction of small hydropower plants (SHPPs). These projects allow harnessing a large hydropower potential of the region and are a significant element of a strategy of Azerbaijan of the so-called Green Energy Zone. The overall installed capacity of the developed plants is also being gradually increased and brought into the regional energy balance.

At this time, the projects put into practice have focused both on power plants restoration and extension

and modernization of electricity networks. Simultaneously, encouraging alternative energy sources and adopting energy management systems have not only brought many benefits to the energy security of the region but also economic and social recovery processes.

Table 1 shows several renewable energy plants that are planned to be commissioned in the Karabakh and East Zangezur region during 2021-2025 and the installed capacities.

Table 1.

Renewable Energy Power Plants in the Karabakh and East Zangezur Regions (2021–2025)

No.	Power Plant	Type	Location (District)	Commissioning Year	Installed Capacity (MW)
1	Gulabird HPP	Hydro	Lachin	2021	8
2	Sugovushan-1 HPP	Hydro	Tartar	2021	4.8
3	Sugovushan-2 HPP	Hydro	Tartar	2021	3
4	Kalbajar-1 SHPP	Hydro	Kalbajar	2023	4.4
5	Kalbajar-2 SHPP	Hydro	Kalbajar	2023	3.6
6	Lachin SHPP	Hydro	Lachin	2023	8
7	Zangilan Solar Power Plant	Solar	Zangilan	Project stage	240
8	Jabrayil Solar Energy Park	Solar	Jabrayil	Project stage	100
9	Kalbajar–Lachin Wind Energy Project	Wind	Kalbajar / Lachin	Planned	100–150

Source: Estimated by the author based on data from the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, “AzerEnerji” OJSC, and various open official sources.

The potential of renewable energy in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions in the so-called Green Energy Zone in 2021-2024 is in the following approximate [1;2;5]:

- Solar energy $\approx 7,200$ MW
- Wind energy $\approx 2,000$ MW
- Small hydropower plants: restoration and reconstruction of more than 30 SHPPs is planned (≈ 500 MW potential).

The entire potential of the region in terms of renewable energy is estimated to be more than 10,000

MW. The Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions have a structure of renewable energy resources that show that solar energy has the most significant amount of resources and potential of about 7,200 MW, which is more than 70 percent of the total potential. Second is the wind energy of about 2,000 MW [5]. Also, the mountainous topography of the region and water resources represent good conditions to develop small hydropower plants.

Diagram 1 shows the structure of renewable energy potential in the economical areas of Karabakh and East Zangezur.

Diagram 1. Renewable Energy Potential of the Karabakh Region (MW)

Source: Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2021–2024). Renewable energy potential within the green energy zone in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions. Baku; generalized by the author.

Diagram 2 provides the percentage distribution of the total renewable energy potential in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economical regions.

Diagram 2. Distribution of Renewable Energy Potential in the Karabakh Region (%)

Source: Generalized by the author based on data from the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2023) and the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2024).

Development of Digital Infrastructure. Digital transformation policy applied in the Republic of Azerbaijan is significant in socio-economic development of regions. The model of the smart village implemented in the Zangilan district of Aghali village is one of the projects that have been conducted in this direction [6]. The project is designed in the context of the Digital Transformation Strategy of the country and presupposes the implementation of the modern information and communication technologies in the rural setting.

As per the available reports, the project is projected to cover almost 100 percent of fiber-optic internet in the region. This infrastructure is the primary technical foundation of high-speed data transmission and the productive use of digital services. At the same time, residential houses built in Aghali village are supplied with alternative energy sources, and all houses are equipped with solar panels. This is a highly valuable approach with respect to the intensification of energy efficiency and the broadening of the application of renewable energy sources.

In addition, smart irrigation and monitoring systems have been implemented in the agricultural sector. These systems allow the monitoring of soil moisture and plant development in real time. E-health and e-education services are operating in regard to the digitalization of social services. Due to the official data provided, over 200 personal residential houses have been constructed in Aghali village and these houses have been incorporated into a single digital utility system.

Urban Planning Indicators and Ecological. Ecological sustainability and the implementation of the modern urban planning principles are one of the key points of the concept of the smart village [6]. Based on the urban development plan, the green areas are expected to occupy over 30 percent of the total territory. This is one of the indicators regarded as crucial in keeping the ecological balance and enhancing the quality of living environment.

Constructing standards of energy efficiency are used in the construction process and residential buildings are built according to such principles as thermal insulation, the use of alternative energy system, and effective use of resources. Besides this, there are rain water harvesting and reuse systems that are put in place to promote good management of water resources. Another plan that is already anticipated in the development of the urban development is the establishment of bicycle lanes and walking paths, which will lead to the creation of green transport and the suppression of carbon emissions.

Analysis. Due to the introduction of such projects, the supply of energy in the Karabakh region has become much more stable. The rehabilitation of small hydropower facilities and the development of new power plants have added energy to the local output and helped to restore agriculture and local economic activities.

Efficient and uninterrupted distribution of energy has been guaranteed by the installation of power plants. The alternative energy projects are oriented to maintenance of ecological balance and further energy independence in the region. The availability of solar and wind energy sources have also generated more job opportunities to the local communities and maximized the energy expenses.

The energy production and distribution optimization, technical losses minimization, and continuous energy supply have become possible with the implementation of smart grid and digital management systems. The use of these systems also adds to the energy strategy of the region in the long run.

Conclusion. The analysis carried out demonstrates that the projects of the Smart City adopted in the Karabakh region are a realistic and holistic approach to the sustainable development strategy of Azerbaijan. The 7,200 MW solar power, 2,000 MW wind power, and hundreds of MW hydropower potential of the region forms a strong base of renewable energy-based development. In the meantime, the state investment that

was distributed in 2021-2025 has reached almost 21.5 billion AZN, which has allowed developing the infrastructure at a pace and systematic rate.

The green urban planning principles, fiber-optic infrastructure, the energy-efficient construction standards, and digital management systems are the key to the ecological and technological transformation of the area. A real example of how digitalization and alternative energy should be applied in a rural setting is the Aghali "Smart Village" model.

Therefore, Karabakh model is not only a post-conflict reconstruction idea, but also a strategic way of how to create a green and smart urban system of the future. This experience has a strong scientific and practical value on the national and international levels regarding sustainable urban development.

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